

A Quantum Guitar

Bob Coecke¹²³

¹Quantum Brain Art Ltd
108 Kennington Road, Oxford, UK

²Wolfson College
University of Oxford, UK

³Perimeter Institute
Waterloo, Ontario, Canada

bob.coecke@gmail.com

Abstract. A guitar string represents a wave, and by associating a qubit to each of its playable states we get a quantum wave. This is the principle behind our Quantum Guitar: ‘quantising all strings of a guitar’. In order to achieve this quantisation, we couple a guitar with Moth’s Actias quantum synth, and for qubit manipulations including measurements the musician uses foot controllers – hence using all four limbs like a drummer. Our Quantum Guitar also allows for smooth continuous transition from ‘quantum’ to ‘classical’ sound, and vice versa. We have used our Quantum Guitar in several live performances in a variety of venues, playing a number different musical styles, hence demonstrating that it is a very uniquely versatile and reliable instrument. For example, in some performances Quantum Guitar was used in industrial music, by the band Black Tish, who are currently recording an album with it. In other performances Quantum Guitar represented a qubit within a sonified Bell-pair under measurement, the other qubit being mentally realised with a Grand Piano. Classical-quantum and quantum-classical transitions prove particularly useful in musical performance. A demo video of Quantum Guitar is also available.

1 Introduction

Some four years ago, for the 1st time a piece of music was composed with the use of a quantum computer, by a team under the pseudonym Ludovico Quanthoven [1]. With the arrival of the field of quantum music more broadly [2], we need dedicated new ‘quantum musical instruments’. These could be entirely new, or, could be the result of augmenting existing instruments. The latter would enable one to quantum-enhance familiar modes of musical expression, that is, some familiarity of playing is retained. But, also, radically new playing opportunities and entirely different sounding music should be aimed for. The latter likely will require very different playing techniques, including new sophisticated coordinated uses of the musician’s limbs.

Different genres will require different instruments. By its very nature, one area of interest for electro-acoustic experimentation is Industrial Music [3, 4], a musical genre that has experimentation with sound at its heart. One could say that Industrial Music is the Musique Concrète ‘of the people’. Musique Concrète, in the early 1940’s, with composers like Schaeffer, Boulez, Stockhausen, Varèse and Xenakis, made use of typically pre-

recorded unconventional sounds.

Electrical guitars have been key to development of Industrial Music, with pioneering bands like Throbbing Gristle, Cabaret Voltaire and Einstürzende Neubauten all employing guitar-alike instruments, besides more experimental instruments just like in Musique Concrète.

Figure 1: Pioneers of Industrial like Music Throbbing Gristle, Cabaret Voltaire and Einstürzende Neubauten all employed electrical (regular or bass) guitars.

Currently Industrial Metal bands like NIN produce soundtracks for major Hollywood movies and have been introduced in the Rock’n Roll Hall of Fame. Key ingredients of the genre have been integrated in virtually any musical style, such as metal, R&B and rap, and all of elec-

tronic dance music is a direct descendent. From 2024 onwards, the industrial band Black Tish started to incorporate quantum music, most notably in 2024 at Wacken Open Air, one of the (if not the) most prominent metal festivals in the world. The band – who retrospectively has been dubbed a pioneer of industrial music [5, 6] – is now recording an album entirely with Quantum Guitar.

What makes a guitar unique among musical instruments is that the musician has the sound-generating substrate literally at their finger tips, which allows one to not only play with the traditional ingredients of music, but also exploit great scope for sound manipulation. For electrical guitar in particular, bends, overtones, damping, use of a tremolo bar, slide etc. provide a wide spectrum for experimentation, especially when used with effect units that can emphasise and/or interact with these features, and therefore its broad use in Industrial Music.

In this paper we describe a Quantum Guitar, that we have put together, and already used in live performances. These include academic events, major public science festivals, and most notably, proper high-profile music venues, with the latter always posing an extra challenge. The development went through a number of experimental phases, some which failed, and some which worked remarkably well. We report here on the current architecture which, as just mentioned, already has proven itself as a battle-ready axe in a variety of circumstances.

A cornerstone for our Quantum Guitar is Moth’s Actias, which is greatly inspired on the earlier Q1Synth [7] due to Miranda, Thomas and Itaboraí. However, previous uses never reached the full musical expression by a single musician that is now achievable by Quantum Guitar, in particular, how we manipulate the qubit.

The 1st use of Quantum Guitar was at the Edinburgh Science Festival (Figure 5). Other performances that have taken place paired Quantum Guitar and Rakhat-Bi Abdysagin on Grand Piano, performing the Composition “Bell” from [8]. Some will also happen for Quantum Guitar and Baroque Organ, including in Edinburgh’s St Giles’ Cathedral, clearly demonstrating Quantum Guitar’s musical versatility.

2 High-level design

The basic idea of Quantum Guitar is as follows:

- (1) A guitar string represents a wave, and by associating a qubit to each of its playable states we obtain a quantum wave, i.e. quantisation of a guitar by means of quantising its strings.
- (2) As all hands/fingers are needed for ordinary guitar playing, in order to control the extra degrees of freedom that come with this quantisation the musician uses their feet, just like a drummer uses all four limbs.

Moreover, one important aspect of this quantum instrument that has been somewhat overlooked in the past for other quantum instruments is:

- (3) One can transition continuously between quantum and classical sound, the latter being ordinary electrical guitar.

Just as it is the case for a drummer, Quantum Guitar requires sophisticated coordination of four limbs, and hence is a new instrument that requires substantial playing practice for adequate artistic exploration of the augmented sound space. The musician evidently needs to be seated for the performance in order to use both feet at the same time when manipulating the qubit, or for performing classical-quantum transition.

Here are the key high-level ingredients of our Quantum Guitar:

- a midi-controlled quantum synth – sonify qubit
- a midi-pickup – generate midi data
- midi foot controllers – capture qubit rotations
- midi foot switches – perform measurements
- two volume control pedals – classical vs. quantum

In addition, in order to overcome the limitation of a guitar’s relatively short-lived notes:

- Use a sustainer pickup for generating continuous quantum sound.

Alternatively:

- Use a good quality delay pedal and/or a high-end reverb pedal could achieve this as well, and add an extra creative sonic element.

3 Concrete implementation

Figure 2: View of our Quantum Guitar setup, using Actias for sonification.

The devices we use are (see Figures 2, 3 and 4):

- We employ Moth’s Actias synth for sonification of the qubit. This allows rotation of the qubit in any possible manner, as well one measurement of the qubit. Obviously Moth’s Actias software is experimental, and that comes at a prize, as we discuss below.

Figure 3: Detailed Quantum Guitar setup part I. The guitar is equipped with a high-quality reliable midi-pick-up (Fishman) and a sustainer pick-up that generates long maintainable notes (Fernandes). The guitar both generates ‘classical’ and ‘quantum’ sound at the same time.

- We use a Fishman midi pickup system that has proven to be very good quality, very reliable and works well enough with Actias. Given the continuous spectrum of frequencies and other features of guitar playing, one needs a very good quality midi pickup that doesn’t miss out on ‘note off’s’, and translates playing with bends and tremolo bar appropriately using pitch bends.
- We use Boss EV-1-WL midi expression pedals to manipulate the qubit. They also prove to be very reliable and work well with Actias, especially when used with a USB cable. While we only use two pedals, we can also cover the third qubit rotation needed for all qubit manipulations, due to an internal switch feature of the Boss EV-1-WL pedal. The use of only two pedals is justified by the fact that we are working with a single qubit, so “green” (see Figure 4) is not supposed to change the state. For demonstration purposes it is still good to have “green” at hand.
- For measurement we use a Boss foot-switch like FS-6 in ‘momentary mode’ – ‘latch mode’ won’t work.
- We use Boss FV500L/H volume pedals since their increased size and weight allows for subtle precision.
- For obtaining a continuous sound we use a Fernandes sustainer pickup, as shown here in the picture. Alternatives that we have explored and also

Figure 4: Detailed Quantum Guitar setup part II. Reliable midi foot controllers (Boss) and a foot switch are used in order to rotate and measure the qubit. Volume pedals are used to independently control the ‘classical’ and the ‘quantum’ sound. One can recognise the colours corresponding to the Actias display on the two midi controllers, which control the corresponding rotations. In this setup, “green” and “orange” cannot be used independently.

work are ‘long’ delays and high-end reverbs with ‘infinite’ capability.

The setup-for a live performance looks as in Figure 5, with a projection of Actias in the background.

4 Troubleshooting and suggestions

Troubleshooting with Quantum Guitar as it is:¹

- Not many guitars with tremolo bar allow for the Fishman pickup. Besides the here shown (now discontinued) Fender EOB, another favourite for us are variants of the Ibanez Prestige AZ.
- Actias sometimes loses its preset, although that never seems to happen when in use. It does happen when putting a midi controller of and on.
- Unplugging and replugging sometimes requires deleting an external midi device, and introducing it again. This seems mostly a problem with an Akai MKII keyboard that we use for testing.
- In Figure 5 we use two laptops each with their audio interface, one for Quantum Guitar, and another one on which we run Logic Pro. Having everything on one laptop doesn’t function reliably.
- Actias does not work on a tablet, as the web-based version doesn’t properly connect to external midi.

¹ Some of these were tested in collaboration with Moth.

Figure 5: Quantum Guitar setup for a live performance at Edinburgh Science Festival, with projection screen for Actias projection.

Other suggestion for Actias:

- Rather than only Z-measurements, it would also be good to have X-measurements as primitive, without the need for rotation to realise them. This would substantially increase playability.

5 Demo video

A demo of Quantum Guitar is available at:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pr4Wr8fdsL0>

6 Some past and planned performances

These include:

- Quantum Guitar talk/demo and performance of “Bell” in Vienna on the occasion of world quantum day:
https://vienna2025.qiss.fr/Welcome-event_Musicevening.pdf
at Berlin Medienhaus of the Universitaet der Kuenste, 11 July (see Figure 6):
<https://www.udk-berlin.de/veranstaltung/quantum-music-concert-2/>
and at Holywell Music Room, Oxford, 23rd November 2025.
- Performance of Rakhat-Bi Abdysagins’s “Quantum Universe” Symphony for Organ, Quantum Guitar and Electronics at Merton College Chapel, University of Oxford, 20th November 2025, and at St Giles’ Cathedral Edinburgh, 23rd August 2026.
- VIP/Press release of Quantum Guitar at Wacken Open Air festival, convened by the Chief Editor of Metal Hammer magazine, July 2026.

Figure 6: Flyer from a performance in Berlin.

7 Tech rider

Playing the Quantum Guitar requires the following:

- a good quality PA for which two XLRs are provided, with good quality stage monitor;
- a big screen for which an HDMI output is provided, which can either be a projection or a large monitor/television;
- an arm-less semi-high chair with adjustable height, and if available, some minor back-support is welcomed, such as in Pictures 2 and 5);
- some good quality drinks.

8 Conclusion and outlook

Quantum Guitar is an instrument that truly augments an instrument in all of its uses, an electrical guitar (including tremolo bar), to a quantum musical instrument, and does so without any sacrifice of its ‘classical features’, both in terms of playability and sound. In particular, it is playable by a single person because no use of hands is required for the quantum enhancement, thanks to using foot controllers. Of course, its most innovative features:

- retaining full classical playability and sound
- the quantum-enhancement being hands-free

can be used for also turning other musical instruments into quantum musical instruments, for example Quantum Violin, Quantum Wind Instrument, Quantum Percussion. The specific use of specific pedals, which have proven to be reliable, can also be directly copied.

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